

EXPLORATION ON THE PREPARATION OF TOWNSHIP TERRITORIAL SPACE PLANNING IN THE CONTEXT OF PARK CITY - TAKING THE WENHUA TOWN, ANYUE COUNTY AS AN EXAMPLE

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ABSTRACT

Since the Central Rural Work Conference in 2017 first proposed to take the road of socialist rural revitalization with Chinese characteristics, all townships have been actively exploring the road of rural revitalization that conforms to local characteristics. Right now, since February 2018, "Park City" has been promoted, and a series of measures have been implemented, which are of great significance to the sustainable development of urban and rural areas. It is of great strategic significance to explore a road to rural revitalization under the background of park cities and to implement the construction and implementation of township spaces.

The Anyue County Party Committee and County Government attaches great importance to it, actively organizes, conducts in-depth research, and successfully completes the "Territorial spatial master planning of Wenhua Town, Anyue County", which not only aims to realize the formation of intensive and efficient production space, moderate living space, and ecological space with beautiful scenery and safety. The harmonious, open, efficient, attractive and quality territorial space pattern has laid a solid foundation for the construction of a lemon culture agricultural tourism town, and also reflects the concept of some park cities. This paper conducts research and discussion on its planning formulation, summarizes the formulation of the existing township-level territorial space master planning, and puts forward some innovative suggestions for rural revitalization in the context of park cities.

KEYWORDS

Rural Revitalization, Park City, Territorial spatial planning, Lemon Town, Smart village.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research background

In recent years, because of the progress of urbanization, to improve the quality of rural areas development is still a serious problem in our developing country. The migration of the rural population has made the rural population ageing. In 2019, the urbanization rate in China has exceeded 60%, which has led to the increasingly hollowing out of the countryside. Seriously, the resulting problems such as abandoned farmland and hardened land affect the sustainable development of the countryside and the happiness of the people. In addition, due to the migration of rural population, there are fewer young farmers in the new generation, lack of professional talents in rural planting, weakening of farming skills, and decline in the quality of agricultural

products. The seriousness of problems in rural areas have also become stronger, and the old production methods lacking of intelligent and green has also caused many problems, such as animal and plant pollution, soil erosion, and the quality of agricultural products has become worrying, which affects the basic requirements of rural and urban people's future life, it is extremely important to solve these problems.

In February 2018, when Chinese President Xi Jinping inspected Chengdu, he emphasized the need to highlight the characteristics of park cities and take into account the ecological value. The concept of park cities was first proposed. Actively exploring and continuing to promote the construction and development of high-quality park cities, Chengdu, Chongqing, Suining and many other cities have formulated plans and are gradually conducting in-depth exploration of the construction methods of park cities. Park City is a high-level form of urban development that fully reflects the new development concept. It is an overall remodeling of the connotation of modern urban construction, which means an all-round change in urban construction mode, urban management mode, citizen lifestyle, and social governance mode. This requires us to apply the new development concept to the whole process of urban planning, construction, management and operation. This concept of sustainable development is also very suitable for the current rural development. The construction of the countryside still needs to firmly grasp the ecological restoration, and create a park with the “scenery and village integration” temperament and unique rural construction, management, production, and lifestyle to revival.

1.2. Research significance

With the establishment of the Ministry of Natural Resources, the preparation of territorial and spatial planning is being carried out step by step. Township territorial space planning plays an important role in transmitting county-level planning from the top, controlling township-level planning in the middle, and guiding village planning downwards. As an attribute of the basic unit of planning, township territorial spatial planning has become a priority to be explored and implemented in spatial planning at all levels. According to the requirements of the development and construction of villages and towns, it is of great practical significance to do a good job, clarify the current situation and problems, and formulate the territorial spatial planning of townships and towns that meets the requirements of the state and can solve important practical problems in rural construction, which is also an important way to achieve rural revitalization. In this study, sorting out the work of the cultural town and integrating the concept of the park city model can be regarded as a simple innovation attempt to open up a unique road of exploration for rural revitalization. the role of roads.

1.3. Basic overview of the research site

Wenhua Town of Anyue County is located in an important agricultural product area in the main functional area of Sichuan Province, mainly focusing on agricultural production. Its specific location is located at the central intersection of the Chengdu-Chongqing metropolitan area, the Nan-Sui-Guang (Nanchong, Suining, Guangan) urban dense area and the “two circles-two wings” of the southern Sichuan urban dense area. It covers an area of 75 square kilometers and governs 3 communities and 12 villages of Shifo, Xinmin and Yueyuan. The total registered population of Wenhua Town is 40,500, of which the non-agricultural population is 4,200. The urbanization rate of the registered population is 10.35%. The GDP is 605 million yuan, the per capita GDP is 15,000 yuan, and the three industrial structure is 44:26:30. It has open cooperation platforms such as the National Modern Agricultural Industrial Park, the World Lemon Industry Development Conference, the World Lemon Variety Expo Park, and 3A-level tourist attractions, and has a certain development foundation in lemon-related industries such as lemon planting, rural tourism, and lemon exhibitions.

Through the investigation, it can be clearly seen that Wenhua Town has obvious location and transportation advantages. It is located in the heart of Chengdu and Chongqing, with convenient transportation. The resource environment is excellent, the ecological background is good, and the resources of mountains, rivers, forests and fields are complete; in terms of industrial economy, the lemon industry has begun to take shape. The prototype, the tourism development momentum is good. However, Wenhua Town also have obvious problems. The above-mentioned typical problems of population outflow, hollowing, and aging are serious, and problems such as abandoned farmland and land hardening also exist. At the same time, there are gaps in the protection of cultivated land and permanent basic farmland. The efficiency of construction land is low, and the potential for consolidation is large; there are many debts in public facilities, and the quality of urban construction needs to be improved.

Under the great attention and strong leadership of Wenhua Town, Anyue County government and relevant departments, the overall planning of the cultural town and town-level territorial space has been compiled and completed, and the “Territorial spatial master planning of Wenhua Town, Anyue County” (hereinafter referred to as: Wenhua Spatial Planning) has been formulated and completed, on the basis of proposing solutions to related problems, it also has certain compilation characteristics. Therefore, first of all, some research and discussion are made on the content of its national land space planning.

2. THE CORE IDEA OF COMPILING THE SPATIAL PLANNING OF WENHUA TOWN

2.1. Adhere to national requirements and firmly grasp the basic points of planning

In the process of compiling the Wenhua Spatial Planning, it closely follows the relevant requirements put forward by the central province and city, and strives to achieve ecological civilization, high-quality development, modernization of the governance system, and integration of multiple plans. The first is to achieve the “integration of the two plans”, to continue the content of the overall management and control of soil plans, the transmission of indicators up and down, and to continue the refined management and control of urban planning, the allocation of development supporting elements, and the attention to space quality; the second is to reflect comprehensive renovation requirements for the whole area. The construction land indicators should be reserved to ensure the development of rural industries and project. The scope of land remediation and ecological restoration has been required and delimited; the third is to reflect the requirements of rural revitalization, focus on industrial development, ecological protection, human settlements and other contents, and fully complete the guarantee of industrial space and new business space, The specific requirements that has been implemented in terms of stabilizing the ecological pattern, optimizing the rural spatial layout, guiding the construction of villages, and improving rural facilities; fourth, completed the adjustment and reform of township administrative divisions (Figure 1), improved the public service facility system, conceived the development model of townships, formation of village planning transmission and guidance. Finally, planning to promote the reform and development of the central town, highlighting its industrial characteristics and development trends, proposing specific and differentiated development guidance measures, and implementing them into the end-point construction projects. The perfect combination is integrated into the planning and preparation content, and 6 aspects have been completed.

Figure 1. Administrative division adjustment map of Wenhua Town in Anyue County

2.2. Do a good job in the basic work of space planning, sort out related issues and lay the foundation

To complete the territorial spatial planning, we must find out the status quo and problems. In the process of compiling the Wenhua Spatial Planning, four aspects are mainly completed. The first is to find out the current situation of the town, especially the core area, summarize and sort out the information provided by relevant departments, find out the basic situation of population, economy, industry and environment, and implement them to specific points through actual research; the second is to unify the base-maps from different departments, and the base map is converted according to the land use classification conversion rules, and the key content of urban space is refined. After that, the land is divided into three categories, two categories, etc.; All-round suitability analysis (Figure 2) has formed a comprehensive analysis and evaluation of the importance of ecological protection, the suitability of agricultural production, and the suitability of construction; finally, according to the specific situation of data integration, the characteristics and problems are sorted out, and the detailed analysis is carried out. Regional transportation, ecological locality, industrial environment, population structure, and land space were analyzed, and the existing problems were summarized, which provided the basis for the subsequent specific solutions.

Figure 2. Analysis map of three types of land use in Wenhua Town, Anyue County

2.3. Grasp the core points of the problem and create township characteristics around the development orientation

In the upper-level planning, the development orientation of the cultural town “China Lemon Culture Agriculture and Tourism Town” has been determined, and it strives to become a demonstration town for the integrated development of Chengdu-Chongqing central axis boutique agriculture, culture and tourism, and a cultural exchange and expo site for China's lemon industry (Figure 3). In actual work, focusing on building this characteristic core of Lemon Town, customizing the planning objectives of the near, medium and long-term phases, using specific strategies such as optimizing the layout, value-added efficiency, comprehensive renovation, and facilities, on the one hand, it systematically solves the aforementioned foundations. On the other hand, it also lays the foundation for the construction of township characteristics, for shaping the characteristic township culture, and laying a solid foundation for the sustainable development of the township.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the planning effect of Lemon Town in Anyue County

2.4. Implement the construction planning unit guidance method to promote further construction and implementation

In the planning, detailed village planning is guided through unit planning (Figure 4), and the control the urban development boundary is strengthened. Try to use unit control and planning

area and other control boundaries, urban development and major projects. Contradictions and conflicts between constructions, according to the permanent basic farmland protection goals issued by the superiors, delineate the permanent basic farmland transfer, reserve and transfer areas. On the premise of avoiding important ecological functions and not occupying or occupying less permanent basic farmland, according to the development direction and scale, according to the requirements of the guidelines to demarcate and implement the boundary, the tourist scenic spot and the withdrawal of the township original town are determined according to the scale of land use, development needs, etc. Whether it is included in the development boundary. Implement the forest land protection goals issued by the city and county, strictly control the use of forest land, promote the replenishment of forest land resources, delineate the protection scope of forest land resources, and strictly control the use of forest land. The safety bottom line of disaster prevention and risk avoidance, the clear development and utilization goals, the delineation of mineral resources prohibited development zones, the clear protection and utilization measures, and the implementation of the mining and recovery technology for the two remaining brick factories are important means of “mining-ecological” balance. The mining process and the restoration process are fully integrated to minimize the impact on the landform environment during the mining work. Under this plan, it is estimated that in 2035, the upper limit of water resources utilization will be controlled within 13 million m³, the amount of forest land will not be less than 1,392 hectares, the amount of public welfare forests will not be less than 956 hectares, the cultivated land will not be less than 3,988.30 hectares, and the permanent basic farmland will not be less than 3,988.30 hectares. Below 3023.02 hectares.

3.2. Improve the industrial development system and consolidate the pillar of Lemon Town

Park city emphasizes the economic value of green and low carbon, and there must be green production methods to develop the economy. In view of the implementation of the requirements of the rural revitalization strategy for industrial prosperity, ecological livability, rural civilization, effective governance, and affluent life, the regional industrial function of the Wenhua Town is determined to be a demonstration town for the integrated development of high-quality agriculture, culture and tourism in the central axis of Chengdu and Chongqing, and a cultural exchange of China's lemon industry Export site. By sorting out the current situation and advantages of industrial development, optimizing the industrial system in the town area according to the integrated development approach of the three industries, promoting the revitalization and development of rural areas, and striving to form a modern agricultural industry as the core, with the ecological tourism industry as the support, and the lemon cultural and creative industry as the feature industrial system. Coordinate the industrial development direction and industrial land demand, plan the industrial space layout, and build the “1+1+N” agricultural industry system with the lemon industry as the leading, the grain and oil industry as the foundation, and vegetable planting and breeding as the characteristic (Figure 5). “One park, two districts and multiple points” agricultural industry layout.

Figure 5. Planning map of the modern agricultural industry system in Wenhua Town

3.3. Determine the space development policy and build the ridge of Lemon Town

Park City emphasizes the humanistic value of cultural people. In Wenhua Spatial Planning, based on the natural geographical pattern, rationally construct ecological barriers and corridors, define development and protection areas, axes and important nodes, determine the overall spatial pattern of the country, and determine the overall spatial pattern of the country as “one center, one screen, two districts and four axes” (Figure 6). By adjusting the administrative division of the town, a four-level town and village system consisting of one central town, two new-type communities, five central villages, and seven grass-roots villages is determined, and the population and construction scale are clarified. Combined with the comprehensive land consolidation plan, fully respecting public opinion, and trying to gather in central villages and agglomeration and upgrading villages, 29 settlements are planned and selected, with a total scale of 71 hectares and a population of 14,000. On the premise of meeting the needs of 72 hectares of villages for centralized resettlement, 91 hectares of urban and rural construction land, and 20 hectares of vacant land, the remaining quota for new urban construction is 41 hectares. Through the aforementioned methods, the gathering and blending of people was completed first. At the same time, the concept of “rural life circle” was implemented, and the public service facilities in the town area were improved according to the three-level structure of “town level-group level-village level”. With the overall orientation of “lemon gardens, integration of scenery and towns”, a pattern of “one ring, four districts, six corridors, and multiple points” has been constructed in the scenic area (Figure 7), and a greenway system has been constructed for characteristic tourism towns and towns combined with the layout of the tourism industry, planning to form two types of greenway systems, “biking trails” and “travel trails”, improving the infrastructure construction of cultural tourism services. Combining humanistic and ecological elements, delineate key landscape management and control areas, put forward requirements for landscape management and control, and focus on guiding the village's style from the four aspects of ecological environment elements, village public space, village public facilities, and village residential buildings to promote the formation of villages.

Figure 6. Planning map of the overall pattern of land and space in Wenhua Town

Figure 7. Landscape planning map of Wenhua Town

3.4. Sort out the characteristic cultural context and build a ladder of lemon towns

Park City emphasizes the aesthetic value of living poetically. Wenhua Town strengthens ecological restoration in the planning, implements the action of “cleaning, rectifying, increasing, and optimizing” according to local conditions, promotes greening beside the village, beside the house, waterside, and roadside, rationally distributes small and micro wetlands and green spaces, and increases the amount of ecological green. The protection and restoration project of mountains, rivers, forests, fields, lakes and grasses, and rural environmental management, build a green space system structure of “one core, four points, two screens and two wedges”. Sorting out the list of historical and cultural heritage protection, clarify the scope of protection, delineate key protection areas, and put forward management and control requirements. For ancient cypress trees in Long'en Village, Huang Ge trees in Wanlin Village, and 8 Huang Ge trees in Shifo Community, the protection scope shall be delimited by not less than three meters outside the vertical projection of the canopy, and new or expanded buildings (structures) within the protection scope of ancient and famous trees are prohibited. It is forbidden to damage ancient and famous trees.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE CHARACTERISTICS AND KEY POINTS OF THE COMPILATION OF WENHUA TOWN SPATIAL PLANNING

4.1. Current highlights and advantages

4.1.1. The system has completed the delineation of three lines, forming the protection of ecological space

The foundation of park city construction is to form the protection of ecological space resources. The completion of the three-line delineation of national land space planning is the basic work of implementing the country. Regional spatial protection and production development have laid a solid foundation. The bottom line has been set for the utilization of important spaces such as forest land, cultivated land, and historical and cultural resources, and the control of national land space has been compulsorily completed with strong control measures and will greatly promote the formation of high-quality green development space in the later construction of the park city.

4.1.2. The planning for the utilization of land and space has been completed in a relatively complete and comprehensive manner

The content of the national territorial spatial planning is comprehensively completed. The first is to complete the development orientation of the Wenhua Town and build the target system of the upper-level planning; the second is to systematically formulate strategies and development directions for the industrial space, and plan the layout of the industrial space; the third is to complete the overall pattern of the town space and public service layouts (Figure 8), proposed measures for development and protection, and gave the reasons and purposes for the adjustment of the spatial structure, exemplified the methods of land and space renovation and restoration, and promoted land and space renovation with specific projects; the fourth is completed the planning of history, culture and features, guided the township government resident planning in the form of unit control, and guided the resident land use control, road traffic, public service facilities, municipal infrastructure, green space system, “four-lines” management and control, and spatial form guidance all arrangements and plans have been made.

Figure 8. Planning map of public service facilities in Wenhua Town

4.1.3. Have precise and perfect positioning, and use this as the core to create features

The Wenhua Town Spatial planning is precisely built concentrating on the positioning goal of building a “Chinese lemon culture agricultural tourism town”, closely relying on the industry as an important building core, and promoting the construction of lemon culture. Promoting the construction of a functional area for the integrated development of the lemon industry makes it a unique highlight of cultural production in the Chengdu-Chongqing Economic Belt. Strengthen cooperation, integrate into regions, develop diversely, and shape characteristics. For the planning of land space and land use, we have firmly grasped the core development point of lemon industry and cultural tourism town, thus forming short-term and long-term planning goals. Promote the construction of relevant characteristic industries and form a good construction system. At the same time, it protects important urban historical and cultural landscapes, integrates landscape and cultural elements into the construction of Lemon Town, and forms a characteristic landscape.

4.2. Key points to be optimized

It should be said that The Wenhua Town Spatial planning has been well done in some aspect, which can become a good guidance and model of relevant spatial planning. However, there are still places where the planning can be improved and optimized. So we will discuss in detail the places where the planning can be improved and improved.

The Wenhua Town Spatial planning based on the concept of Park City has achieved certain results, and plays a certain effect. However, there are still deficiencies. Firstly, there need more means to practice intelligent planning in town construction and management. The Park City also emphasizes the value of healthy and pleasant life. When applied to rural construction, it is shown that more modern science and technology methods should be used, which is very important for building a dynamic and vibrant countryside; Secondly, there is a lack of means to improve and optimize land. In fact, land use can be implemented into the comprehensive optimization of soil quality, and some new technologies with reasonable price and wide applicability can be used to improve the quality of land production; Thirdly, the implementation of industrial production and lemon culture can be implemented to specific landscape sketches and public service facilities, and the products and buildings can be refined and deepened; Finally, there should be an economic support system and landscape theory system that can make the countryside daily operation well. Therefore, relevant application in these part should be considered in detail.

4.3. Innovative and optimized ideas under the concept of park city

4.3.1. A system of “sponge” + economic production + rural park can be built

Wenhua Town has the typical hilly characteristics of towns and villages in Sichuan. As an important planning core, Lemon Town can be built according to the situation on the mountain, using the topography to create unique natural scenery and sustainable economic situation. The method is also very important to the same type of village construction. Basing on current water and soil environment, it is recommended to use sponge ecological infrastructure to build a water cycle ecology and enrich the building facade environment and space courtyard environment of Lemon Town, which can optimize the quality of soil and make a economic way in rural development. As for building construction, the rainwater tank system, the flower bed water collection system, and the garden infiltration (Figure 10) can be used for renovation. Besides, it only needs very low economic investment coupled with technologies such as automatic irrigation and pouring system control and humidity detection, which enhances the reuse of water resources and saves resources while enriching the landscape. The regulation and storage system can be used for solar energy control, temperature control and scientific and technological filtration. These applications can be popularized and practiced in China or other country. Water storage and water transportation can be used to conserve land, cultivate orchards and gardens, promote the economical utilization of water resources, and form a more hierarchical rural park complex. There is no corresponding plan in the original plan, and in the subsequent construction plan, a system of rural water resources utilization can be formed, and the water utilization space planning can be improved with the household as the unit.

Figure 10. Schematic diagram of transformation of rainwater tank collection, high-level flower bed collection and rainwater garden infiltration facilities

4.3.2. Industrial planning should conform to the concept of smart pastoral

To promote the construction of smart rural planning, which can be done well in village construction. The characteristic Lemon Town has formed a complete guide for the industry. Although the industrial planning has implemented the requirements of rural revitalization, clarified the functions, sorted out the direction, analyzed the needs, and planned the space, specific guidance for wisdom construction or development guidance should be formed in the prominent aspect, beyond the basic content. That is to say, a more in-depth and specific development model-oriented research should be made, and a more complete guiding concept can be made for the implementation of the industry, the attraction of talents, and the construction of the business format. In fact, the land use in the current spatial planning use the technology of data integration, such as “one map”. But these methods are still limit in urban planning and design. In core smart-development industrial policy support, there need more. Talent introduction measures, and guaranteed projects can all be put forward systematically, and more innovative planning can be carried out in terms of means, broadening the horizons of talents, deducing planning and packaging methods to activate sleeping resources, and conceiving Internet+ in the industrial smart planning, WiFi coverage, the Internet of Things transportation, smart production, site recommendation, multimedia promotion and other forms are guaranteed, so as to add the wings of the 5G+ to the development of townships (Figure 11).

In terms of implementation, the technology of ICT industry is doing well in our country, which is an important method for construction of smart village. So, in order to promote the progress, firstly, government leaders in the town should set an example under the guidance of relevant cultural departments of the county, and take the initiative to take the responsibility of promotion. By using the popular advanced platform, such as Tik-tok, a good brand for culture of lemon town can be formed; Secondly, the government can organize some special cultural activities in important seasons such as flowering and harvest to form a localized Lemon Culture Festival. Propagating to the surrounding city at first place, and using the internet platform to increase the popularity of it to surrounding cities and provinces then, to make it a well-known activity which lay a solid foundation for future further development; Thirdly, to encourage local residents, farmers, relevant enterprises and other beneficiaries and stakeholders of direct industries to carry out webcast and online promotion activities, which can make the lemon culture more famous; Fourthly, relevant online knowledge education can be promoted. For example, children can learn lemon science culture, lemon plant knowledge and surrounding flower education in Wenhua lemon town. For the cultivators of related industries, using online teaching breeding can attract more industry participants.

Figure 11. Smart pastoral for countryside

4.3.3. More lemon spacial cultural town marks and landscape nodes should be created

As an important planning core, lemon culture should be more deeply embedded in village construction and style and characteristic guidance in addition to industrial planning and guidance. In terms of village construction, some lemon elements we can be considered. The lemon culture should be considered as the core. To create some town mark which is full of lemon elements in the center of the town, and set several nodes by some sculpture and scenery. In addition, we can set up teaching, entertainment, understanding, and exhibition spaces for lemon culture in territorial space, not only industrial In the functional area, relevant content can also be configured in the village resident space, so that the culture can be more systematic in the style and appearance. The shaping of distinctive urban scenic spots can greatly enrich the spatial hierarchy of villages and towns, attract people and strengthen the vitality of villages and towns.

On the other hand, overall style design architectures in the town should be carefully considered, mainly in residential and industrial buildings. Doors and windows decoration on buildings, facade wallpaper, architectural colors, etc., these all can use traditional Sichuan characteristics and add lemon elements. Not only in the industry areas, but the architecture nearby can use a unified style. Only in this way can the culture be more systematic in style. As an important implementation plan, the design of lemon culture can be integrated into a series of infrastructures such as sketch sculptures, walking paths, lighting, sketch facilities, etc. in public spaces, so as to enrich the utilization of lemon culture in space style and create a spatial appearance of complex function (Figure 12). Such construction needs to be planned into a system, and the capital is also a consideration on the one hand. Therefore, we can start from the core point, by the construction of new buildings and landscape node landmarks, and gradually complete the construction with the industrial development and sufficient capital.

Figure 12. Lemon space with complex function planning intention map

4.3.4. The economic support strategy system of lemon development in Wenhua town

Based on current affair, a core problem restricting rural revitalization is human resources and economic resources. In fact, these two problems stem from the fact that the development and construction of villages and towns need certain economic support, and the economic support needs certain construction resources and human flow. Therefore, reasonable economic support strategies and systems are the cornerstone of the cultural development of lemon industry, which are also the way to realize the concept of smart production and Park City.

Wenhua town should choose suitable and capable agricultural production enterprises, which has a management and business strategy skills. Although there are relevant enterprises in Anyue, the business strategies need to be improved, especially the follow-up road of intelligent sustainable development and the road catering to the concept of Park City. This should be conducted by characteristic quality marketing. Story marketing can be used to arouse people's interest. Stories

relevant to the unique industrial development of lemon town is needed. The STP analysis method is adopted for the lemon town market. Industrial development orientation and urban development orientation should match, by comprehensive market research and judgment, which can further broaden the lemon business. The Wenhua town can cater to the young people's preference for milk tea and drinks, as well as the middle-aged and elderly people's preference for health preservation, explore the characteristic products of lemon health culture and formulate the strategy of lemon-health, complete the fine division of labor of lemon industry.

Specifically, Basing on the low-cost smart pastoral management, basic industrial construction and sponge concept, Wenhua town can build the “Internet of Things” system of smart agriculture. Before forming a large-scale and systematic industry, it is necessary to build smart infrastructure, complete smart management, real-time operation, remote operation and other means, and improve the comprehensive quality of the industry. When the industry forms a scale, Wenhua can promote the expansion of production and modern processing to realize the deepening productivity and improving quality of the industry. Then, completing the three-level promotion of the industry by “local famous - regional famous - national famous”(Figure 12), and realizing the ultimate goal of industrial development.

Figure 12. Lemon space with complex function planning intention map

4.3.5. Create a theoretical system of park towns and villages in line with rural revitalization

Based on the exploration and research of the theoretical system of the park city, it is necessary to implement the relevant theories in rural areas, and also to form a relevant system research and knowledge framework, and establish a park town and township theory with relevant index evaluation, design methods, and management systems. Based on the current situation of villages and towns, we can use the Reverse-space-building theory to give priority to the protection of ancient trees, concentrating development on the existing greening, break the previous tradition method of giving priority to enclosure and land planning. Carrying out new one starting from green space and landscape protection, and then enclosure for residence, public service and municipal facilities, gather the population, which can contribute to sustainable development (Figure 13). The theoretical system of economic and cultural parks and towns has become the new development direction of Rural Revitalization and urban-rural integration. In this process, realizing the three-stage promotion of intelligence from point to line, and then to surface is necessary to implement the theoretical system of intelligent development of Park City in towns with rural revitalization.

Figure 13. The difference between traditional way and new way

5. CONCLUSION

With the steady progress of spatial planning and the integration of multi-planning, the tasks of territorial spatial planning at the township level have been gradually rolled out. It should be said that the relevant concepts of the Park City and smart village can be fully reflected in the construction and planning of the countryside, and play a very good role, but there is no suitable road yet. Through the analysis and summary of Wenhua Town, some basic characteristics and measures to be improved are put forward. In the follow-up, we will continue to conduct in-depth research. Taking this as the starting point, we will strive to form some theories and play a good role in the revitalization of the village.

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